

Enhancing Pink Aesthetics in Periodontics through Gingival Depigmentation : A Case Report

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Abstract

A radiant smile greatly enhances an individual's character and exudes confidence. The overall appeal of a smile is influenced not only by the alignment, shape, and colour of the teeth but also by the gingival tissues. Gingival pigmentation occurs due to melanin granules produced by Melanoblasts. Although melanin pigmentation in the gums is completely harmless and does not pose any medical issues, complaints about "black gums" are common, particularly among individuals with a high smile line. Various depigmentation treatments have been documented, including bur abrasion, partial thickness flap, cryotherapy, electrosurgery, and laser therapy. In this study, we compare the outcomes of laser therapy and electrosurgery over a period 6-month follow-up period.

Keywords : Electrocautery, Gingival depigmentation, Hyperpigmented Gingiva, Oral Pigmentation Index, Scalpel Surgery

Introduction

Gingival health and appearance are crucial for a captivating smile, and removing unsightly pigmented gingiva is essential for a pleasant and confident smile. The colour of healthy gingiva is typically described as "coral pink." Melanin, the most common endogenous pigment, causes gingival pigmentation and is found in the basal layer of the gingival epithelium. Gingival hyperpigmentation, often referred to as physiological or racial pigmentation, is considered a genetic trait seen in various ethnic groups. It can also be linked to conditions such as Addison's disease, Peutz-Jeghers syndrome, and neurofibromatosis.¹

Gingival pigmentation appears as a diffuse, deep purplish discoloration or as irregularly shaped brown, light brown, or black patches, striae, or strands. This pigmentation is primarily localized at the anterior labial gingiva and is more common in females than in males. Although melanin pigmentation of the gingiva is completely benign and poses no medical issues, many patients, particularly those with a high smile line, often express concern about "black gums."

In hyperpigmented gingiva, there is an excessive deposition of melanin in the basal and suprabasal cell layers of the epithelium. Melanoblasts, located between the epithelial cells in the basal layer of the gingival

epithelium, produce melanin, leading to gingival pigmentation. The degree of pigmentation varies among individuals and depends on a variety of factors, especially melanoblastic activity.²

Aesthetics play a crucial role in modern dental practice. In 1994, Pal et al. presented a study on the psychological impact of "black gums." The findings revealed that many people are conscious of their pigmented gingiva, with females being more aware than males. The majority of participants believed that pigmented gingiva poses an aesthetic problem.³

Oral Pigmentations can be classified on the basis of aetiology, distribution, and severity. Dummet oral pigmentation index (DOPI) is the commonly used index due to its simplicity and ease of use.⁴

The scores are as follows:

No clinical pigmentation (pink-coloured gingiva)

Mild clinical pigmentation (mild light brown colour)

3. Moderate clinical pigmentation (medium brown or mixed pink and brown

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colour)

Heavy clinical pigmentation (deep brown or bluish black colour)

Gingival depigmentation is considered a reconstructive periodontal procedure that involves removing hyperpigmented gingiva using various methods. The choice of method should primarily be based on clinical experience and individual preferences, with a strong emphasis on achieving improved aesthetics. Different techniques for depigmentation include Scalpel technique, Cryosurgery, Electrosurgery, Lasers - Nd: YAG laser, Er: YAG laser, CO2 laser, Diode laser, various chemical agents and method aimed at masking the pigmented gingival from less pigmented gingival areas (Free gingival graft, Acellular dermal matrix allograft), etc.⁵ In this paper, we compare the results of Laser and electrosurgery technique with a follow-up period of 6 months.

Case Presentation

A 26-year-old female patient visited the Department of Periodontics and Implantology, expressing concern about the dark colour of her gums affecting her aesthetics. She mentioned that the pigmentation had been present since childhood, suggesting physiological melanin pigmentation. The patient's oral hygiene was poor, but she was in overall systemic health.

Fig. 1- Hyperpigmented Gingiva in Maxilla and Mandible.

Fig. 2- After Complete Scaling and Root Planing.

In the initial phase of treatment, scaling was performed. We opted for laser depigmentation on the maxillary arch, electrosurgery for one half of the mandibular arch. The entire procedure was thoroughly explained to the patient, and written consent was obtained. A comprehensive medical and family history, along with blood tests, were conducted to rule out any contraindications for surgery.

Case 1- Depigmentation By Laser

Local anaesthesia was administered in the maxillary anterior region from premolar to premolar (Lignocaine with adrenaline in a 1:100000 ratio by weight). Depigmentation was performed on the maxillary arch from the right premolar to the left premolar using a diode laser. The maxillary arch was treated first, followed by the mandibular arch a week later using an electrosurgery unit.

The procedure involved using the laser tip in contact mode on the pigmented gingiva, parallel to the root surfaces, and the area was then cleaned with saline-soaked gauze. The patient remained comfortable throughout the surgery, and there was no bleeding. A periodontal pack was placed, and postoperative instructions were provided. The patient was recalled after one week for re-evaluation (fig. 5), and she reported no pain in the treated area.

Fig. 3- Laser depigmentation by diode laser in maxillary arch.

Fig. 4- Depigmentation by Diode laser

Fig. 5- Post 1 week healing after laser depigmentation by diode laser in maxillary arch.

Fig. 8- Post 1 week after depigmentation by electro-surgery

Case-2 By Electro-surgery Unit

Similarly, epithelial excision was performed on the right side of the mandibular arch using the electro-surgery unit with a loop electrode. Avoid excess heat build-up and unintended tissue damage. Special attention was given to avoid contact with the periosteum, alveolar bone, and vital teeth to avoid exposing the bone on the attached gingiva and to ensure minimal removal of tissue on the marginal gingiva to preserve gingival harmony.

Fig. 6- The electro-surgery unit used for depigmentation

Fig. 7- Depigmentation by electro-surgery

Post-surgical antibiotics (Amoxicillin 500mg, three times daily for five days) and analgesics (ibuprofen with paracetamol, three times daily for three days) were prescribed after both the procedures. The patient was instructed to use chlorhexidine mouthwash every 12 hours for one week.

The patient was seen for a follow-up appointment at the end of one week (fig. 8). The healing process was proceeding as expected, and the patient reported no discomfort. It was advised to continue using chlorhexidine mouthwash for another week. By the end of one-month, complete re-epithelialization had occurred, and the healing was deemed satisfactory. The patient did not experience any post-operative pain or sensitivity. During the six-month follow-up, the gingiva appeared healthy, with no signs of further pigmentation (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9- 6 month Post operative picture

Discussion

Oral pigmentation is present across all human races. There are generally no significant differences in oral pigmentation between males and females. The intensity and distribution of pigmentation in the oral mucosa vary not only between races but also among individuals within the same race and within different areas of the mouth. Physiological pigmentation is likely genetically determined, although Dummet (1960) proposed that environmental factors such as mechanical, chemical, and physical stimuli may influence its extent (Cicek, 2003).

Melanin pigmentation often results from melanin deposition by active melanocytes primarily located in the basal layer of the oral epithelium. Pigmentations can be addressed for aesthetic purposes, and various treatment approaches have been utilized for this purpose (Pontes et al., 2006). The choice of a gingival depigmentation technique should consider clinical expertise, patient affordability, and individual preferences.

Electrosurgery demands greater expertise compared to scalpel surgery. Prolonged or repeated application of current to tissue can lead to heat buildup and unintended tissue damage. Care must be taken to avoid contact with the periosteum, alveolar bone, and vital teeth (Ozbayrak et al., 2000).

Although lasers are increasingly used for gingival depigmentation, there is limited information on their application. They are recognized for effectively treating gingival hyperpigmentation, offering superior aesthetic outcomes and a lower recurrence rate compared to other methods. Patients generally experience comfort during laser procedures, minimal bleeding, and favourable post-operative results, supporting their use for depigmentation. However, laser systems require sophisticated equipment, significant space, and are costly. Alternatively, a free gingival graft can also be employed to eliminate pigmented areas. However, it requires an additional surgical site (donor site) and colour matching (Mokeem, 2006). These treatment modalities, however, are not widely accepted or popularly used.

Scalpel surgical technique is highly recommended in consideration of the equipment constraints that may not be frequently available in clinics (Almas & Sadiq, 2002). It is known that the healing period for scalpel wounds is faster than other techniques. However, scalpel surgery may cause unpleasant bleeding during and after the operation, and it is necessary to cover the exposed lamina propria with periodontal dressing for 7 to 10 days (Almas & Sadiq, 2002). Post surgical repigmentation of gingiva has been previously reported. Repigmentation is described as spontaneous and has been attributed to the activity and migration of melanocytic cells from surrounding areas (Mokeem, 2006)

Conclusion

There are wide varieties in gingival colour in normal healthy people. Gingival colour is determined by degree of vascularization, the thickness of the keratinized epithelium and the amount of the pigment-containing cells. The latest methods for gingival depigmentation in today's dental practice include cryotherapy, free gingival autograft, and laser treatment and these methods have accomplished satisfactory outcomes.

The utilization of scalpel scrapping method for depigmentation is the most feasible as compared to other techniques, which require more advanced armamentarium. However, scalpel method causes unpleasant bleeding during and after the surgery, and it is necessary to cover the surgical

site with periodontal dressing for 7 to 10 days.

A major shortcoming of electrosurgery is that its repeated and prolonged use induces heat accumulation and undesired tissue destruction.⁶ Bhusari et al 2011 evaluated efficacy of electrosurgery and scalpel technique, 3 patients were treated by split mouth design. Earliest signs of re-pigmentation started at 6 months interval and it was observed that repigmentation was more pronounced in electrocautery than scalpel technique.⁷ Prasad et al 2005 evaluated the response of electrosurgery and combination of bur scrapping and scalpel technique. Electrosurgery showed desirable results, followed by epithelial excision and bur abrasion methods which showed a slight recurrence of pigments.⁸ This case report highlights the successful use of a laser diode, electrosurgery unit and scalpel for gingival depigmentation.

In our case series we found that superior to other techniques, application of a laser results in homogeneous ablation of epithelial and rete pegs as well. Diode laser with 810 nm wavelength is used in soft tissues for coagulation and cutting. Diode laser irradiation also has bactericidal effect resulting in hemostasis.⁹ Having a high affinity to penetrate into haemoglobin and melanin pigments makes it the preferred laser for depigmentation of gingiva. Diode lasers can be used both in pulsed or continuous mode. Application of the laser in pulsed mode prevents overheating of surrounding tissues that may cause necrosis and jeopardize healing. Taking into consideration the previously published studies,^{10,11,12,13} diode laser was used in continuous mode in this study knowing the fact that it may penetrate deeper and affect connective tissue as well. That's why, the evaluations were also made at weeks 1, 2, 4. The use of lasers has several advantages such as no need to place a periodontal dressing, short healing period, no or very slight pain, no haemorrhage. The only disadvantage may be the high cost of the lasers. The patient experienced no complications and reported high satisfaction with the results, with no recurrence of pigmentation observed after three months.

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